

POISSON RATIO EQUAL TO 12 IN LONGITUDINAL COMPRESSION DURING MESO-FE ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE TEXTILE REINFORCEMENTS

D. Wang¹, N. Naouar¹, E. Vidal-Salle¹, P. Boisse^{1*}

¹Université de Lyon, LaMCoS, INSA-Lyon, F-69621, Villeurbanne, France

* Corresponding author (Philippe.boisse@ins-lyon.fr), <http://lamcos.insa-lyon.fr/>

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ABSTRACT

At mesoscale, the tows of a composite reinforcement are considered as solids made of a continuous medium in contact with their adjacent materials. These tows are usually tensioned, but some loads in the reinforcement lead to a state of longitudinal compression. The tows, composed of a large number of fibres, exhibit a special behaviour when subjected to longitudinal compression. The local buckling of the fibres means that the compressive rigidity of the material used to represent the tow is much lower than when it is under tension. In addition, longitudinal compression leads to significant transverse expansion. It is established in this work that transverse expansion could be represented by a Poisson ratio that was approximately constant when the length of the tow and compressive stress varied. The buckling of the fibres substantially increases the transverse dimensions of the tow, which leads to a high Poisson ratio (up to 12 in this study). Longitudinal compression and transverse expansion were incorporated into a mechanical tow model. Mesoscale finite element simulations of reinforcement with binding yarn subjected to longitudinal compression have shown that these improvements have led to results consistent with micro-CT tests.

1 INTRODUCTION

Meso-scale finite element (FE) modeling of textile reinforcements considers the preform as a set of yarns in contact with their neighbors. These yarns are seen as continuous materials. Most analyses are carried out on periodic reinforcements and concern the Representative Unit Cell (RUC). This RUC is the smallest elementary pattern making it possible to obtain the entire reinforcement by translation. Among many applications, mesoscopic analyses are used to determine homogenized properties [1, 2] or damage initiation and development. Mesoscopic simulations of the RUC deformation during forming make it possible to determine the internal geometry of the yarns constituting the deformed reinforcement [3]. This geometry conditions the permeability of the deformed reinforcement during injection. The geometry of the yarns after forming also influences the mechanical properties of the final composite.

In most mesoscopic analyses of composite textile reinforcements, the yarns are under tension. Nevertheless, considering the internal geometry of the reinforcement and the interlaces due to weaving, some yarns may be in a state of compression in the direction of the fibers (longitudinal compression). This is particularly the case during the compaction phase of a reinforcement that precedes the injection phase in an LCM process. If the reinforcement has binder yarns or yarns through the thickness (z-yarns), these can be in longitudinal compression. Experimental analysis and simulation of the behavior of composite reinforcement yarns in longitudinal compression is the topic of this work.

The transverse expansion during longitudinal compression of a fiber yarn is analysed in this work. This expansion is important given the individual buckling of the fibers during longitudinal compression. The individual fibers buckle but the yarn, seen as a continuous material at the mesoscopic scale, expands by the Poisson effect.

Some studies have been carried out to determine the Poisson ratio of fiber yarns. They concern the transverse strains of yarns under tension [4]. However, to the best of our knowledge, there are no analyses of the transverse expansion of yarn in longitudinal compression, and this is the main goal of the present paper. It was shown by experiments that the ratio between the transverse expansion and the

longitudinal compression was relatively constant for different compression ratios and various yarn dimensions. Consequently, one can propose a Poisson ratio which defines the transverse expansion of the yarn. The value of this ratio can be substantial (e.g., 12 for the reinforcement in Fig. 1).

The constitutive law taking into account the measured longitudinal compression and transverse expansion was used for the mesoscopic simulations of the compaction of the RUC of a composite reinforcement (Fig. 2 to 5) [5]. The deformation of the yarns in longitudinal compression obtained by these simulations was found to be in good agreement with the experimental deformation achieved by X-ray tomography.

2 FIBER YARN MESOSCOPIC MODEL

The yarns that were considered in this study were assumed to be a set of parallel fibers as shown in Fig. 1. Meso-FE modelling of the yarn requires a constitutive law that conveys the specific fibrous nature of the yarns that are assumed to be continuous solids made of fibers, in a single direction. Among continuous mechanical models at large strain, rate constitutive equations are widely used [6, 7]. They relate the stress and strain rates:

$$\underline{\underline{\dot{\sigma}}}^{\nabla} = \underline{\underline{C}} : \underline{\underline{D}} \quad (1)$$

The objective derivative is defined from the rotation $\underline{\underline{Q}}$ of the rotated frame:

$$\underline{\underline{\dot{\sigma}}}^{\nabla} = \underline{\underline{\dot{\sigma}}} - \underline{\underline{\Omega}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\sigma}} + \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\Omega}} = \underline{\underline{Q}} \left(\frac{d}{dt} \left(\underline{\underline{Q}}^T \cdot \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \underline{\underline{Q}} \right) \right) \cdot \underline{\underline{Q}}^T \quad (2)$$

In case of fibrous material, the rotation must follow the fiber [8, 9]:

$$\underline{\underline{Q}} = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{f}}}_i \otimes \underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}_i^0 \quad (3)$$

Figure 1: X-ray tomography imaging of a fibrous yarn

Consequently, the strain field in the yarn's cross section can be decomposed into a spherical part and a deviatoric part [9]:

$$[\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}_t]_f = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_s & 0 \\ 0 & \varepsilon_s \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_d & \varepsilon_{23} \\ \varepsilon_{23} & -\varepsilon_d \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

ε_s is the spherical strain component and ε_d and ε_{23} are the deviatoric strain components. This decomposition leads to the following constitutive relations:

$$\begin{cases} \Delta\sigma_s = A\Delta\varepsilon_s \\ \Delta\sigma_D = B\Delta\varepsilon_D \\ \Delta\sigma_{23} = B\Delta\varepsilon_{23} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Finally, the constitutive matrix [C] is expressed as:

$$[C] = \begin{bmatrix} E & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & \frac{A+B}{2} & \frac{A-B}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & \frac{A+B}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & G_{lt} & 0 & 0 \\ \text{sym} & & & & B & 0 \\ & & & & & G_{lt} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

This mesoscopic mechanical model is used to simulate the deformation of a very unbalanced textile composite reinforcement presented in Fig. 2. It is composed of glass fiber yarns: warp yarns, weft yarns and binder yarns. The warp yarn was much larger than the other two.

Figure 2: X-ray tomography imaging of an unbalanced textile reinforcement

A transverse compaction of the textile reinforcement, shown in Fig. 2, was carried out inside an X-ray computed tomography system. The textile reinforcement was compacted between two Plexiglas plates, $\varepsilon_{\text{compaction}}=44\%$. The micro-CT analysis gave the experimental deformed geometry of the yarns of the fabric after compaction (Fig. 3). The simulation of this global compaction was carried out using the mesh of the RUC, as shown in Fig. 4. The deformed shape obtained by simulation (using the constitutive model presented above) is shown in Fig. 5. The simulated shape of the binder yarn was not correct. It presented wrinkles that were not observed in the micro-CT analysis. In addition, the width of the deformed binder yarn was smaller than the experimental one. This binder yarn was subjected to longitudinal compression which could not be correctly modeled by the constitutive law presented above. In the sequel, the longitudinal compaction behavior and the related transverse expansion are analyzed and taken into account in the constitutive model.

Figure 3: Deformed geometry of the yarns of the fabric after compaction.

Figure 4: Meso FE mesh of the RUC

3 POISSON RATIO IN LONGITUDINAL COMPRESSION

The initial shape of the constitutive matrix Eq. (6) neglects the transverse expansions. This is fairly well justified if the yarn is under tension. When the yarn is in longitudinal compression, the cross-section of the yarn increases significantly (Fig. 6). It is thus necessary to take into account this transversal expansion in the mechanical behavior. For this, a Poisson ratio ν_{lt} is introduced into the constitutive matrix

Figure 5: Simulation of the compaction

Figure 6: Poisson ratio in longitudinal compression

$$[D] = [C]^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_t} & -\frac{\nu_{lt}}{E_t} & -\frac{\nu_{lt}}{E_t} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{A+B}{2A \cdot B} & \frac{B-A}{2A \cdot B} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & \frac{A+B}{2A \cdot B} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & \frac{1}{G_{lt}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ sym & & & \frac{1}{B} & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & \frac{1}{G_{lt}} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad [C] = [D]^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} E_t & \nu_{lt}A & \nu_{lt}A & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{A+B}{2} & \frac{A-B}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & \frac{A+B}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & G_{lt} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & B & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & G_{lt} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

The Poisson ratio ν_{lt} introduced in Eq. (7) was determined by an inverse approach based on simulations of the longitudinal compression tests with transverse expansion and corresponding experiments (Fig. 6). Fig. 7 shows the obtained Poisson ratio for longitudinal compression in the range 0.25%–4%. Different lengths and widths of the specimen were considered. The obtained Poisson ratios of the fiber yarn varied with these factors. However, these variations were rather low. In a first approximation, for the sake of simplicity, a constant value of the Poisson ratio may be considered. For the binder yarn analyzed in the present work, the Poisson ratio was close to 12.

Figure 7: Poisson ratios measured for different dimensions and longitudinal compression strains

4 MESOSCOPIC SIMULATIONS TAKING INTO POISSON RATIO

Figure 8: Transverse compaction of an unbalanced textile reinforcement.

The unbalanced textile reinforcement presented in Fig. 2 was compacted by 44%. This simulation was carried out in Fig. 5 with the original constitutive law and led to spurious buckling of the binder yarn. The simulation was now performed with the models of eq. (7) for longitudinal compression and transverse expansion. The deformed shapes obtained by these simulations were compared to the

experimental micro-CT images of the deformed fabric in Fig. 8. Buckling of the binder yarn was avoided and a correct transverse expansion was achieved when the yarns were modeled as proposed in Eq (7). A correct transverse expansion was achieved (Fig. 18d). Some other examples can be found in [5].

5 CONCLUSION

The transverse expansion of a yarn in longitudinal compression is large. The Poisson ratio expresses the buckling of individual fibers in the behavior of the yarn seen as a continuous material. It was shown in the present paper that a constant Poisson ratio could be identified for glass fiber yarns and that the value was substantial (equal to 12). Mesoscopic simulations taking into account longitudinal compression and transverse expansion gave results in good agreement with the experimental deformations obtained by micro-CT analysis. The fibers buckle and lead to an important transverse expansion. The fibers are moving away from each other. The hypothesis of a continuous medium for the yarn, that supposes any mesoscopic analysis, is probably more questionable than for the yarns in tension.

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